

Internal shearing in compound landslides and consequences on retention structures

Nahmed Nissar, M.S.

Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University (Virginia Tech)

Alba Yerro, Ph.D., M.ASCE

Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University (Virginia Tech)

ABSTRACT

Perceiving the mechanics involved in the deformation process of landslides and the eventual interactions with structures is necessary for risk assessment. This work focuses on the study of internal failure mechanisms that develop in compound landslides. In addition to the resistance offered by basal shear surfaces, internal shearing also influences compound landslides' stability and kinematics. For compound landslides, internal shearing is essential to develop feasible sliding mechanisms. The internal deformation accumulates along the shear bands (or shear zones) that develop within the sliding mass, and their location is generally attributed to slope changes along the basal sliding surface or topography (i.e., biplanar or curved surfaces) that constrain the landslide's strain field. The development of these internal shear bands also controls the energy dissipated during the motion, the material degradation, and even more importantly, the impact force against structures and protective barriers. A theoretical model of a compound landslide is numerically analyzed using the Material Point Method (MPM), a state-of-the-art numerical technique appropriate to model large deformation problems. The internal failure pattern is identified for different basal sliding geometries. A generalized internal failure mechanism is proposed for biplanar and curved compound geometries. The material degradation and energy dissipation are evaluated in terms of the accumulated deviatoric strain and the reaction forces exerted by the landslide on a vertical wall.

Keywords: compound landslide, internal shearing, biplanar sliding surface, Material Point Method

INTRODUCTION

Landslides are natural disasters and cause enormous damage to humankind and property every year. Roughly 25-50 people lose their lives annually in the United States because of landslides (USGS 2020). Primarily, these casualties result from rock falls, debris-flows, flow slides, and debris flow. More than 2,600 fatal landslides recorded between 2004 and 2010 resulted in more than 32,000 casualties (Petley 2012). Therefore, it is imperative to understand the mechanics involved in the mass of a landslide on a large scale. To mitigate landslide damage, protective barriers can be installed on the slope or along the path of a potential landslide. These engineering solutions are designed with the aim to stabilize the slope (e.g., anchors, retaining walls), deviate the path of the mobilized mass (e.g., deflection walls), or slow down and/or interrupt the mass flow (e.g., check walls) to reduce the landslide consequences on critical infrastructure and human lives. For an effective design of these structures, it is important to determine the impact forces resulting from potential landslides and soil masses; hence, understanding the factors that control such forces and the energy of the landslide at the time of the impact is critical.

The stability and kinematics of a slope depend on many factors. The resistance of the basal slip surface is the most relevant in translational slides where the entire body slides in an active state. The internal distortion and

degradation of the material can also influence the stability and kinematics slope, especially in compound landslides. Compound landslides consist of an active block that drives a more stable passive block (Hungr et al. 2014), and motion in more than one direction is required (Figure 1). In this relatively common scenario, internal shearing also affects the kinematics of compound landslides. State-of-practice numerical tools (i.e., finite elements and finite differences analysis) are unable to provide any feedback on the evolution of internal shearing patterns at large strains because they are limited by too much mesh distortion. Within the last decade, advanced computational methods such as the Material Point Method (MPM) have been used to study large deformation problems, including landslides and slope instabilities. However, very limited attention has been paid to investigating how the geometry and properties of the basal sliding surface influence the formation of internal shear mechanisms on landslide kinematics and energy dissipation.

The purpose of this preliminary work is to improve the mechanics understanding of compound landslides. Particularly, the investigation focuses on (i) determining how the geometry and friction angle of the basal sliding surface influence the initiation, shape, and evolution of the internal shearing mechanisms during the landslide process, and (ii) how the different failure shearing patterns control the accumulated shear strains and the final impact forces on a rigid wall. The work is organized into different sections. First, the methodology is presented where the basis of the MPM is introduced. Secondly, a small-scale laboratory slope failure is reproduced as a validation exercise. Then, the numerical model setup is presented, including the input data of a parametric analysis. After that, the results are presented, considering the influence of different factors. Different failure patterns are proposed based on the observations, and a discussion is established, taking into account accumulated shear strain and impact forces on a rigid vertical wall. Finally, the conclusions are summarized at the end.

Figure 1. Schematic illustrations of the failure mechanisms of internally sheared compound slides (modified from Fell, Glastonbury and Huntr, 2007).

METHODOLOGY

This work takes advantage of the capabilities of the Material Point Method (MPM) for the simulation of large deformations and multi-body interactions. MPM was developed by Sulsky et al. (1994). In the Material Point Method, the continuum body is discretized by a predetermined number of Lagrangian particles or Material Points (MP). These MPs carry all the information of the continuum such as mass, volume, density, gradient, displacement, velocity, acceleration, stress, strain, material parameters, strength parameters, etc. In geotechnical engineering problems, the MPs represent a small portion of the entire continuum and not the individual soil grains. Each material point moves attached with the solid body and hence constitutes the Lagrangian representation of the medium. An Eulerian mesh is present, which covers the entire domain in which the body is supposed to move. All displacements and deformations are numerically calculated in this computational mesh. The system of equilibrium equations is solved in the mesh grid, but usually, it does not deform with the body, unlike FEM. Mapping functions are used to transfer the variables from the MPs to the nodes. The conservation of mass is satisfied because each material point contains a fixed amount of mass at all times. MPM can also utilize history-dependent constitutive models, which is extremely helpful for the modeling of soils. Recently, MPM has received a good deal of attention in geotechnical engineering. In particular, Soga et al. (2018) emphasize the need to develop numerical methods that can predict both the failure initiation as well as the post-failure behavior of landslides. The authors discuss the merits and limitations of various numerical techniques for modeling large-deformation problems, including landslides, and suggested MPM overall. Many publications in MPM have focused on landslides and slope instability processes (e.g., di Carluccio et al. 2019; Xu et al. 2019; Yerro et al. 2019; Conte et al. 2020), demonstrating its outstanding capabilities for the study of the whole deformation process during such geotechnical hazards. In particular, Yerro et al. (2016) examined the stability conditions and the post-failure behavior of a deep-seated compound

landslide, inspired in Vajont landslide. The authors analyze the internal shearing patterns and degradation using MPM for both pre-failure and post-failure conditions. Their results indicated that the stability of the compound slope is controlled by an internal shear band which develops along with a progressive failure mechanism. Other MPM works include the study of the impact of granular flows on structures (e.g., Ceccato et al. 2018; di Perna et al. 2022). The work presented herein includes two main parts. First, the MPM software capabilities are demonstrated through a validation exercise. This exercise is followed by a parametric analysis performed on a theoretical slope. All the simulations presented in this work are performed using the Anura3D software (Anura3D, 2021).

VALIDATION EXERCISE

MPM software capabilities are demonstrated through a validation exercise that consists of a small-scale laboratory slope collapse on a bi-planar slope based on Mancarella and Hungr (2010). The experimental setup consists of a 29° downward slope followed by a 33° run-up slope. In that physical model, dry sand is placed at the top of the 29° incline. A volume of 0.027 m^3 of sand is positioned in a box with a triangular cross-section at the top. Once released, the granular material flows down to the bottom of the slope and then climbs up the 33° upward ramp. The basic geometry and material parameters are taken directly from the physical experiment (Figure 2a and Table 1). Plain-strain conditions are assumed; hence the width of the original model (0.35 m) is not considered. The radius of curvature is 0.10 m at the point of slope change (named herein “slope transition” or “transition zone”) in the lowest part of the incline. Figures 2b, 2c, 2d show a comparison between laboratory data and numerical results. The flow profiles at times 0.6 , 1.2 , and 2.0 seconds after the soil is released are illustrated. There is a good agreement of the runout for these time steps, up to 1.2 seconds. At $t=2$ seconds, MPM predicts a slightly higher run-up for the model. This could be because the constitutive model used in this case (i.e., Mohr-Coulomb model) might be too simplistic to predict the grain-to-grain interactions accurately.

Figure 2 MPM results based on Mancarella and Hungr (2010). (a) MPM model, (b)(c)(d) comparison between experiment (on the left side) and the MPM results (on the right side) at three different times.

Table 1. Material parameters of numerical model used for validation.

Parameter	Value
Soil density, ρ	1630 kg/m^3
Friction angle of soil, φ	30.9°
Young's modulus, E	500 kPa
Poisson ratio, ν	0.2
Friction coefficient at the base, μ	0.4

NUMERICAL MODEL

A plane-strain model of a theoretical compound biplane landslide is considered (Figure 3) to investigate the mechanics of compound landslides and understand how internal shearing develops and affects the overall energy in the moving mass. Initially, the soil rests on an incline, making an angle of θ with the horizontal. The basal sliding surface has a friction coefficient of μ . The angle of the soil surface at the toe with the horizontal is β , and b is a representative measure of the thickness of the landslide measured from the “kink” in the direction perpendicular to the soil surface (Figure 3a). The slope transition from the incline to the horizontal portion is defined by the radius of curvature R , which is expressed in multiples of b as $R=nb$, being n the multiplication factor. Note that $R = 0$ corresponds to the particular case of a sharp slope transition (i.e., kink). The height of the slope is H , and the total length of the horizontal plane is X . Finally, a rigid wall is placed at the right end of the model on which the magnitude of the impact forces exerted by the moving mass can be evaluated.

Figure 3b shows the computational mesh and the initial location of the material points of a representative model with $R = 1.5b$. The average element size is 0.25 m, which is small enough to minimize the mesh dependency on the results. The friction along the basal sliding surface is included using a contact algorithm between the base material and the mobilized mass. The right boundary represents the rigid wall, in which only vertical displacement is allowed without frictional resistance. The soil in the slope is assumed frictional ($\phi=35^\circ$) and is simulated using the linear-elastic perfectly-plastic Mohr-Coulomb constitutive model. No dilatancy is considered, and the calculation is in dry conditions. The soil density (ρ) is 1560 kg/m^3 , Young's modulus (E) is 10 MPa, and the Poisson ratio (ν) is 0.3.

Figure 3. (a) Theoretical sketch of a compound landslide with a bi-planar geometry. (b) MPM discretization (mesh and initial location of MPs).

The calculation consists of two different phases. First, the stresses are initialized, applying gravity at the same time. The contact algorithm is not activated, meaning a fully rough contact between soil and base to avoid sliding. Numerical damping of 0.75 is imposed to minimize spurious oscillations during this calculation phase. The second phase comprises the sliding and the impact on the wall and finalizes when a new equilibrium is reached. The damping is reduced to 0.01, and the failure triggering is imposed by activating the contact algorithm; hence sliding is controlled by μ .

A parametric analysis has been performed to study the effects of different characteristics of the basal failure plane on the internal shearing, including (i) the radius of curvature at the transition zone (R), (ii) the initial slope angle (θ), and (iii) the friction coefficient at the contact (μ). While R , θ , and μ are varied according to

Table 2, other parameters remain constant, including $H=8\text{m}$, $X=20\text{m}$, $b=3.6\text{m}$, and $\beta=26.5^\circ$. In this parametric analysis, a total of 16 simulations have been analyzed. Note that extremely low μ has been employed in these simulations to minimize the energy dissipated along the basal sliding surface and isolate the internal shearing processes.

Table 2. Details of the parametric analysis. In all cases: $H = 8\text{m}$, $X = 20\text{m}$, $\beta=26.5^\circ$.

Model no.	θ [°]	b [m]	R	μ
1	45	3.58	0 (kink)	0
2	45	3.58	$0.5b$	0
3	45	3.58	b	0
4	45	3.58	$1.5b$	0
5	45	3.58	$2b$	0
6	45	3.58	$1.5b$	0.08
7	45	3.58	$1.5b$	0.17
8	37	4	0	0
9	37	4	b	0
10	37	4	$2b$	0
11	37	4	$4b$	0
12	37	4	$6b$	0
13	26	3.58	0	0
14	26	3.58	$2b$	0
15	30	2	0	0
16	30	2	$7.35b$	0

RESULTS

This section presents the results obtained from the parametric analysis. The influence of the basal surface characteristics on (a) the internal shearing pattern, (b) the pattern and degree of accumulated strain, and (c) the impact forces against a rigid retaining structure (i.e., rigid wall) are presented herein.

a. Internal shearing patterns:

The evolution of the internal shearing mechanism is presented in terms of the incremental deviatoric strain, which is the accumulated strain during one calculation time step ($\Delta t \approx 0.0005$ s). This quantity allows us to determine the localization and evolution of the shear failure mechanism at each time of the calculation.

Figure 4 shows the incremental deviatoric strain at different times for four reference models. These cases correspond to models 1, 3, 4, and 5 (Table 2). Model 1 has a kink transition, while models 3, 4, and 5 represent curved geometries with increasing R . The basal slope angle ($\theta=45^\circ$) and the basal friction ($\mu=0$) are the same for this subset of simulations. Different failure mechanisms are observed. For the model with the sharp transition (model 1, Figure 4a), the internal shear mechanism initiates at the kink, and a single shear band develops vertically towards the soil surface ($t = 0.5$ s). This initial failure surface clearly separates the sliding mass into two initial wedges: one moving down the incline (active wedge) and the second one being pushed horizontally (passive wedge). As the soil mass moves forward, soil from the active wedge becomes part of the passive wedge, and the kinematically admissible failure mechanism increases complexity. The vertical shear band spreads out as the motion progresses, and a triangular shear zone is observed with the vertex at the kink ($t=1.5$ s). The edges of the shear zone are almost normal to the slip surfaces, and the angle that defines the aperture of the shear zone, α , approximately coincides with the slope angle $\theta=45^\circ$ ($t=1.5\text{s}$). With the progression of the movement, α slightly increases ($t=2\text{s}$) towards the direction of the motion.

Figure 4. Internal shearing mechanism for various compound landslide geometries at different times: (a) model 1, (b) model 3, (c) model 4, and (d) model 5.

The models with curved transition zones ($R \neq 0$) (e.g., Figure 4b,c,d) do not present a single shear band or a single shear zone. Instead, two triangular shear zones develop from the vertexes at the edges of the transition zone towards the soil surface (Figure 4b,c,d). The larger the R , the more clearly the two shear zones can be identified because they are physically more separated within the slope. If R is small enough, the two shear zones can eventually overlap. The aperture of the two shear zones (α) is similar, and like in the kink model, α approximately coincides with the slope angle $\theta=45^\circ$. As the mass moves forward, α of the shear zone closer to the toe slightly increases towards the direction of the motion. In all studied cases, the vertical extension of the shear zones reaches the ground surface; hence the area of the shear zones depends on the thickness of the moving mass as the landslide progresses. Apart from the two shear zones, an arc-shaped shear band (i.e., shear arc) can be distinguished (e.g., Figure 4b and Figure 4c ($t=0.5s$)). The shear arc connects the vertex of the two triangular sheared zones at the endpoints of the curved transition zone (e.g., see Figure 4b). The radius of the shear arc (d) clearly increases with R . Also, when R is large, for the thickness of the slope considered here, the shear arc cannot be identified. This is because when $d > b$, the shear arc intersects the ground surface, and the

remaining segments tend to overlap with the shear zones (Figure 4c). Using trigonometry, a geometric representation of a theoretical shear arc is presented in Figure 5. The analytical value of this radius (r) can be expressed in terms of the slope geometric parameters (R , θ) as:

$$r = R \tan(\theta/2) \quad (1)$$

Expressing the radius of the shear arc measured from the MPM results (d) in terms of the theoretical one (r) as:

$$d = kr \quad (2)$$

Being k the multiplication factor, we observe that k values are very close to 1 ($k = 1.0-1.16$), indicating that both d and r are very similar in all the simulations ($r \approx d$).

Figure 5. Geometric representation of the shear arc.

Overall, the internal shearing patterns obtained with larger friction coefficients (models 6 and 7) are in good agreement with the ones described for the frictionless case. In particular, Figure 6 represents model 6 that has a friction coefficient of $\mu=0.08$ on the basal shear surface. Both shear bands and the shear arc are observed. Also, when different slope angles ($\theta = 45^\circ$, 37° , 26°) are considered (models 8-16), the same patterns are applicable, with the angle defined by the shear zones approximately the slope angle ($\alpha \approx \theta$) or slightly larger.

Figure 6. Internal shear mechanism for model 6 ($R=1.5b$; $\theta=45^\circ$; $\mu=0.08$).

Figure 7 summarizes the internal shearing patterns determined from the parametric analysis. For the kink transition ($R = 0$) (Figure 7a), the initial internal shear mechanism is a vertical shear band that evolves to a unique shear zone. For the curved geometries ($R>0$), two shear zones are observed together with a shear arc that connects both zones. When the radius of the shear arc is less than the thickness of the landslide ($d < b$), the shear arc is fully visible (Figure 7b), otherwise, the shear arc tends to overlap with the shear zones and cannot be distinguished (Figure 7c). The aperture of the shear zone is $\alpha \approx \theta$, but as the motion progresses, α slightly increases up to a certain value $\alpha \approx \theta + \alpha'$, being $\alpha' < 10^\circ$. Despite the small increase of α , the geometry of the internal shearing mechanism, once formed, remains practically constant over time. It is important to highlight that the patterns presented in Figure 7a and Figure 7c can be understood as particular cases of the failure mechanism presented in Figure 7b.

Figure 7. Summary of internal shear mechanisms for different basal transition zones.

b. Effect of the internal shearing patterns on the accumulated shear strain

In this section, the effects of internal shearing on the accumulated deviatoric strain are presented. Cumulative deviatoric strain is directly related to material degradation; hence this analysis is essential to locate the most damaged areas in the mobilized mass after the landslide. Figure 8 presents the accumulated deviatoric strain profiles for three models (models 8, 10, and 12 from Table 2). Different time instances are considered to show the accumulated shear pattern for the same runout. The three geometries are characterized by $\theta = 37^\circ$ and $\mu = 0$; the only difference is the curvature of the transition zone. From Figure 8, it is seen that the mass above the slope transition (active wedge) does not have accumulated shear strain since the material in this zone has not entered the internal shear mechanism, and the basal plane is frictionless. The material that is initially located at the downside (near the toe) of the internal shearing mechanism remains unsheared. Once the material crosses the internal failure mechanism, the strain accumulates along with a band, whose thickness z depends on the curvature of the transition zone. Note that for the kink case ($R=0$, Figure 8a), z is equivalent to the thickness of the landslide. For curved transitions, as R increases, the degradation zone becomes thinner, leaving a band of unsheared material close to the basal sliding surface. This effect is the result of the development of the shear arc described in the previous sections. The magnitude of the accumulated deviatoric strain also tends to decrease with larger R .

Figure 8. Cumulative deviatoric strain different transition geometries for the same runout. (a) $R=0$ (kink), (b) $R=2b$, (c) $R=6b$. All models have $\theta = 37^\circ$ and $\mu = 0$.

c. Effect of the internal shearing patterns on the impact against retaining structures

In this section, we analyze the effect of the internal shearing patterns on the impact forces against a rigid vertical structure. The impact force can be understood as a qualitative estimate of the energy carried by the

landslide. The impact forces are determined on the vertical wall at the right end of the model geometry (Figure 3). Models 8, 10, and 12 are considered here for reference. These have three different slope transitions ($R = 0, 2b, 6b$), $\theta = 37^\circ$, and $\mu=0$. Note that these are the same models presented in Figure 8. The vertical wall is placed at a horizontal distance (X) of 15m. Figure 9 presents the evolution of the reaction forces on the wall with time. Similar trends are observed in all the cases. Consistently, no reaction force is observed until the toe of the landslide reaches the vertical wall. Then, the reaction force on the wall rapidly increases until it reaches a maximum value that is maintained for another period of time. Finally, the force suddenly decreases down to a constant value. At this point, the mass has reached a new quasistatic equilibrium, corresponding to the lateral earth pressure at rest for the final stable geometry.

Although the general trends are similar, the different radius of curvature (R) at the transition zone present relevant differences in the results. First, the maximum impact force increases with R . For instance, the recorded reaction force for the model with $R=6b$ is 530 kN/m, while for the kink geometry, it decreases down to 460 kN/m, a decrease of 13.2%. Secondly, when R increases, the mobilized material impacts the wall slightly faster, which indicates that the kinetic energy of the landslide increases with R .

Figure 9. Reaction forces exerted on a rigid vertical wall for different models ($R = 0, 2b, 6b$).

Overall, these observations are consistent with the accumulated deviatoric strain patterns presented in Figure 8. Rounder slope transitions (larger R) lead to less accumulated shear strain and plastic deformation in the landslide (less material degradation). In turn, this implies less energy dissipation in the mobilized mass, which is translated to more kinetic energy and larger reaction forces on the retaining wall.

CONCLUSIONS

This contribution studies the formation of internal shearing failure mechanisms in compound landslides by means of the Material Point Method. The effects of the basal surface characteristics (i.e., radius of curvature of slope transitions, slope angle, and friction coefficient) are investigated. Based on a parametric analysis, different shearing patterns are observed. A unique shear zone is observed when the slope transition is sharp (kink), while if the slope transition is more rounded, two shear zones are distinguished. The shear zones are triangular regions with the vertex at the limits of the transition zone and the sides approximately perpendicular to the basal sliding surfaces. In addition, a shear arc connecting the two shear zones is eventually observed. This analysis provides a guide to estimate the internal failure mechanism in bi-planar compound slides based on geometric characteristics of the slope. It is also demonstrated that the basal geometries affect the pattern and degree of accumulated strain in the landslide as well as the impact forces against retaining structures (i.e., rigid wall). The results confirm that sharper slope transitions lead to more material shearing and plastic deformation in the slope, which implies that more energy is dissipated in the mobilized mass during the sliding. This reduces the kinetic energy of the landslide and the reaction forces on the retaining wall drop. Based on these results, kink transitions are more dissipative, hence more conservative in terms of damage potential.

REFERENCES

- Anura3D (2021). "Anura3D MPM Software - Tutorial Manual. Version 2021-Centro." Anura3D MPM Research Community.
- Ceccato, F., Redaelli, I., di Prisco, C., Simonini, P. (2018). "Impact forces of granular flows on rigid structures: Comparison between discontinuous (DEM) and continuous (MPM) numerical approaches." *Computers and Geotechnics*, 103, 201-217.
- Carluccio, G., Pinyol, N.M., Perdices, P., Hurliman, M. (2019). "Numerical modelling of Val d'Arán landslide with Material Point Method." In: *Proceedings of the VI International Conference on Particle-Based Methods: fundamentals and applications*. CIMNE, 2019, p. 534–542.
- Conte, E., Pugliese, L., Troncone, A. (2020). "Post-failure analysis of the Maierato landslide using the material point method." *Engineering Geology*, 277, 105788.
- Di Perna, A., Cuomo, S., Martinelli, M. (2022). "Impact Forces and Energy of Flow-like Landslides Against Protection Barriers: a New MPM-validated Empirical Formulation." *Geoenvironmental Disasters*, DOI:10.21203/rs.3.rs-1197305/v1 (in review).
- Fell, R., Glastonbury, J., and Hunter, G. (2007). "Rapid landslides: the importance of understanding mechanisms and rupture surface mechanics." *Quarterly Journal of Engineering Geology and Hydrogeology*, 40(1), 9–27.
- Hungr, O., Leroueil, S., and Picarelli, L. (2014). "The Varnes classification of landslide types, an update." *Landslides*, 11(2), 167–194.
- Mancarella, D., and Hungr, O. (2010). "Analysis of run-up of granular avalanches against steep, adverse slopes and protective barriers." *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 47(8), 827–841.
- Petley, D. (2012). "Global patterns of loss of life from landslides." *Geology*, 40(10), 927–930.
- Soga, K., Alonso, E., Yerro, A., Kumar, K., Bandara, S., Kwan, J. S. H., Koo, R. C. H., Law, R. P. H., Yiu, J., Sze, E. H. Y., and Ho, K. K. S. (2018). "Trends in large-deformation analysis of landslide mass movements with particular emphasis on the material point method." *Géotechnique*, 68(5), 457–458.
- Sulsky, D., Chen, Z., and Schreyer, H. L. (1994). "A particle method for history-dependent materials." *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 118(1–2), 179–196.
- USGS. (2020). "How many deaths result from landslides each year?." [Online] https://www.usgs.gov/faqs/how-many-deaths-result-landslides-each-year?qt-news_science_products=0#qt-news_science_products (accessed January 14, 2022).
- Xu, X., Jin, F., Sun, Q., Soga, K., Zhou, G.G. (2019). "Three-dimensional material point method modeling of runout behavior of the Hongshiyuan landslide." *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 56(9), 1318–1337.
- Yerro, A., Pinyol, N. M., and Alonso, E. E. (2016). "Internal Progressive Failure in Deep-Seated Landslides." *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*, 49(6), 2317–2332.
- Yerro, A., Soga, K., and Bray, J. (2019). "Runout evaluation of Oso landslide with the material point method." *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 56(9), 1304-1317.